

Research Article

Evaluation of Single National Curriculum Implementation in Public and Private Schools at Primary Level in Rawalpindi

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Article Info.	Abstract
<p>Received: 22-08-23 Revised: 27-09-23 Accepted: 29-09-23 Published: 30-09-23</p>	<p>An effective educational system promotes social and economic advancement while assisting a nation in reaching its objectives. Phase one of the Single National Curriculum (SNC) has been introduced in Pakistani public and private primary schools. Through the use of a single curriculum, all students in the nation are to receive an education that is standardized. It was also believed that this would lessen inequality and fragmentation. This study looks at the advantages of SNC in both public and private schools as well as the necessary preparation. This study looked at the application of SNC in elementary public and private schools in Rawalpindi, Punjab, as well as the opinions of the teachers regarding its efficacy and implementation. In this investigation, casual comparability was employed. Using convenient sampling, the researcher selected 50 schools in the Tehsil Kahuta, District Rawalpindi to collect quantitative data. Using quantitative data, the researcher compared the design, execution, and descriptive and inferential statistical methods (mean, standard deviation, and t-test of independent samples).</p>
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Introduction

In any education system curriculum is very important element. Learners join school to learn and what the school plans for them to learn is included in the curriculum. The Punjab School Education Department introduced the Single National Curriculum on August 2, 2021, and it was immediately adopted by all public, private, and Madaris schools in the province of Punjab. To ensure that all students are afforded a chance at a good education in a manner that is just and equitable, there should be only one system of education in place. This system should include a standard curriculum, a single mode of instruction, and a standardized testing environment. One system of education for everyone, including a curriculum, medium, and standardized testing environment.

The adoption of a single national curriculum will result in the creation of educational opportunities that will aid all subgroups of the community in the acquisition of skills that will result in equal chances for upward social mobility. The adoption of a unified national curriculum would not only guarantee equality, but it will also make it possible for students to receive an education that is adapted to their specific requirements. The holistic development of pupils in light of growing social, national, and worldwide trends and in conformity with local objectives is the major purpose of the Single National Curriculum (SNC), which was implemented in South Africa in 2012.

There will be no impediments to the movement of teachers or pupils from one province to another because the guidelines would be followed uniformly across the entire nation. By incorporating it into the various grade levels, it will make sure that the Holy Quran and Sunnah are taught to all of the students. Through the implementation of the Single National Curriculum, it will grow into the ideal state in accordance with the goals that have been set by the national leaders of Pakistan. It has been determined to be necessary to create a constitutional framework for the purpose of accomplishing this goal, as it is in line with national policies, aspirations, and standards.

The Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the United Nations has set the fourth Sustainable Development Goal as "Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote learning opportunities for all." As a result, the creation of constitutes an effort to align with the goals and targets outlined in SDG-4. It is necessary that the new trends in teaching, learning, and evaluation be matched with the Single National Curriculum in order for the country to be able to compete successfully with the rest of the world.

Prior to the development of the Single National Curriculum, numerous comparative studies were carried out to ensure that it was in line with standards prevalent all over the world. The Pakistani, Singaporean, and Cambridge educational systems are important. The academic expectations placed on Pakistani pupils were evaluated next to those in Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia, and the United Kingdom. The conclusions were reflected in the SNC Consultation with various stakeholders. Major stakeholders include public and private schools, all federating units, Federal Government educational institutions (FGEIs), Cantts and Garrisons, Deeni Madaris, Cambridge University in the United Kingdom for English, Mathematics, and Science Lums, and Agha Khan University.

In Pakistan, Religious Education is currently taught to students of all minority groups from grade 1 all the way to grade 12. In the past, students who were not Muslim were required to study "Ethics" from grade 3 all the way through grade 12. The Single National Curriculum places an emphasis on democracy, human rights, sustainable development, global citizenship, personal care and safety, as well as truthfulness, honesty, tolerance, respect, peaceful cohabitation, environmental awareness and care, and sustainable development. Learning that is based on activities, rather than sitting in a classroom all day, fosters analytical, critical, and creative thinking.

The curriculum from 2006 was only used in public schools and private schools with low academic standards. At phase I, the Single National Curriculum is planned to be implemented at all of Pakistan's Deeni Madaris, in addition to public and private schools. SNC was initially implemented in Punjab in 2021 for students in Pre-5th grade. It is used in grades 6-8 in the 2022-23 school year. In any given educational system, the curriculum serves as the bedrock upon which academic achievement is built. It is possible to categorize the curriculum. A nation's life philosophy, ethics, customs, educational goals, and mentality are all reflected in its national curriculum in some way. A state's past, present, and future are all connected by the national curriculum, and the curriculum also looks ahead. People's attitudes, behaviours, and mentalities are shaped by the one national curriculum, but many educational systems with varying curricula and methods generate prejudices, complexes, confusions, and divisions in the population. According to Sehgal (2021), the manifesto of the current administration of Pakistan calls for the creation of a centralized Single National Curriculum and for the curriculum's actual implementation.

The government will adopt the Single National Curriculum in stages, with the first phase beginning in April 2021 with elementary schools. A person's abilities, powers, and capabilities can be severely restricted across a wide range of domains when they have a disability. With the right kind of support, the least restrictive environment, and appropriate accommodations, a person with a handicap can conquer the challenges brought on by their condition and achieve success in life. Ackland et al. (2017).

The curriculum from 2006 was only used in public schools and a few private institutions with lower tuition costs. All schools in Pakistan, including public, private, and Deeni Madaris, will be required to implement the SNC. This research will be meant to investigate the implementation of SNC in public and private primary level schools. The implementation of SNC was divided in three phases. The first phase is implemented and teachers implemented have different point of view regarding its implementation. Its implementation also highlighted some implementation planning issues. Previous literature shows that research has been done on the usefulness of SNC. This study will be conducted in local sense to study the implementation and planning of its phase I. The study will provide knowledge about the planning and effectiveness of SNC by its implementers i.e. teachers. This study will also tell us about planning improvement for the implementation of next phases of SNC.

Review of Literature

Curriculum

The term "curriculum" refers to an all-encompassing term that describes the academic pursuits, teaching methods, and supplementary resources that are included in the instruction of a given school, course, or programme. The definition of "curriculum" that may be found in dictionaries is one that is rarely used in educational institutions. Learning objectives, units and lessons, assignments, projects, textbooks, presentations, materials, and videos, as well as examinations, assessments, and other methods used to evaluate student performance are all included in the curriculum. According to Sinnema, Nieveen, and Priestley 2020, teacher curriculum encompasses learning requirements, as well as lessons, tasks, and materials that are necessary for organizing and teaching a course.

Knowledge to be taught, desired learning goals, a plan to reach them, and tools to evaluate how well the plan is working are all components of a curriculum. Education for everyone is seen as an aspirational objective for proponents of the SNC. The idea of an equitable education system is

appealing to the majority of people in Pakistan since education is unequally distributed in terms of opportunity, access, quality, educational aspirations, and socioeconomic class. The National Curriculum is comprised of standards, aims, goals, and objectives, all of which are founded on extensive research and the collective wisdom of the nation. A country's or state's Single National Curriculum (SNC) ensures that all of the country's or state's children receive the same education. Because to this technique, educational disparities between public schools, private schools, and madaris are narrowed, particularly in Pakistan; as a result, each and every student has an equal opportunity to participate in public education. According to Jahanzaib, Fatima, and e Nayab (2022), a unified educational system will provide all pupils with instruction, a unified curriculum, and standardized testing.

The public school system is responsible for the degradation of all aspects of educational excellence. The primary cause for concern is the absence of investment and oversight on the part of the instructors and personnel. When compared to public schools, private schools invest more money and provide a higher quality of education. However, only religious subjects are covered in madaris. The information that follows demonstrates that Pakistan's educational system is disorganized and patchwork (Panjwani & Chaudhary, 2022).

Since 1947, Pakistan has been engaged in a struggle for national identity, the results of which may be seen in the country's educational policies and curriculums. Pakistan has been able to establish a nation via the cultivation of critical thinking, creativity, empathy, diversity, and the ability to coexist thanks to the high quality education it provides. Long ago, education-based homogeneity became a fundamental goal of Pakistani policy, and this objective remains at the heart of Prime Minister Imran Khan's proposed "SNC" (Tahir, 2022).

The disparity between the curriculum that was adopted and the learning outcomes led the creation of a national curriculum. The learning standards are global prerequisites for efficient learning, whereas the curriculum encompasses all of the educational experiences a child will have during their lifetime. It addresses matters pertaining to the infrastructure, academic and extracurricular activities, content, textbooks, evaluation, and instructional strategies. In comparison to the curriculum from 2006, the government has increased the minimal learning criteria. It is important to regularly reevaluate the curriculum to ensure that it remains relevant in light of shifting social norms (Bari, 2021).

The National Curriculum Council, which is a federal organization, conducts periodical reviews of the changes made to curriculum. The PTI government's platform called for a "Single National Curriculum" to decrease class gaps in teaching and learning, such as religious vs. secular, public vs. private inequities. This was to be accomplished by the implementation of a "Single National Curriculum." They had high hopes that it would level the playing field and increase people's ability to move up the social and economic ladder. The concept of a national curriculum has become more problematic as a result of skepticism regarding the curriculum of a particular organization. Since the 18th amendment, education has been under the jurisdiction of the province government. As a result, the textbook board has the ability to define the curriculum. Sindh did this with the introduction of the SNC.

In 2018, the National Curriculum Committee established a task group comprised of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), educational systems, and subject matter experts to produce curriculum. The real documentation was written by the programmers. Just now, industry experts discussed their strategic perspectives. Workgroups were formed with the participation of instructors from private schools as well as representatives from provincial and federal ministries. They examined research that had been conducted all across the world on this subject, used bubble

studies in a number of different fields, and developed a single curriculum that encompassed all of their recommendations and findings (Rubab, Yousuf, and Dahar, 2021).

Single National Curriculum (SNC)

Since its publication, the Single National Curriculum (SNC) has been the subject of discussion among educators, intellectuals, and members of the media. After the 18th constitutional amendment was passed in 2010, education was decentralized to the provinces in Pakistan. The issue centers on the necessity of a federal curriculum in Pakistan. To further indoctrinate a conservative society, according to critics, the SNC would remove this at the behest of the powerful military institution, which has long opposed the 18th Amendment (Khan & Nadeem, 2020).

The SNC places moral and political goals ahead of cognitive and behavioural development in students attending schools under their jurisdiction. This is demonstrated by the curriculum overview document as well as the arguments provided by the education minister and advisers. According to Durrani and Nawani's research from 2020, the SNC has the goal of bringing religious schools, often known as madaris, on par with public schools.

According to the Western world, Pakistan's madaris are a breeding ground for Islamic extremism and terrorism; hence, the West wants Pakistan to reform and regulate its madaris. Nevertheless, madrasah education has always been contentious, and no administration has ever been able to successfully reform it. Free education, as well as free board and lodging, are typically provided to disadvantaged students at religious boarding schools. Through the years, the administration's position has always been to reject any and all reform proposals. It would appear that the government is being indulgent with religious authorities in an effort to make madaris more acceptable to the general people by including even more religious material in the already abundant public education system. The cricketer-turned-politician Khan uses Islamic symbols and chants to motivate the populace as part of his campaign to take control of a nation that is deeply divided. The demands of religious stakeholders and security lobbyists were taken into consideration during the founding of SNC. Despite the fact that Urdu is a language, philosophy, and media, the Islamic teachings and nationalism are emphasized in the curriculum (Kausar, 2020).

Instead of being treated as a subject, students will study English as a language. This seemingly straightforward idea highlights the fact that language is imbued with its own philosophy, civilization, and ethos. In the new curriculum, English will only be covered in terms of its function as a language and its grammatical principles. How can history, power, culture, morals, literature, and imagination all be separated from language? The designers at SNC don't care about this question. It does this by employing the political aspects of education to assimilate people, which, in turn, standardizes society by enforcing a single culture and denying the identities of different cultures. The process of nation-building being undertaken by Pakistan.

Students' ability to be creative and think critically would suffer as a result of school-based brainwashing, which is counterproductive to the educational mission. Children who are taught certain opinions at a young age are unable or unwilling to evaluate or question those beliefs. Students are encouraged to accept religious or political ideals without being challenged when they receive this education. According to Ahmad, Sultana, and Jamil (2021), critical thinking is the process of utilising facts and reasoning in order to grasp concepts, judgements, ideas, and actions.

Opponents are also concerned about the provision of education in Pakistani languages other than Urdu. Equal consideration must be given to the norms, practises, and beliefs held by each group if social justice and respect are to be achieved. Proponents of diversity argue that educational diversity should mirror cultural variety. There are 66 different languages spoken in Pakistan, including Urdu, Punjabi, Pashto, Sindhi, and Balochi. According to Amirali and Halai (2021), a national curriculum ought to incorporate all of the most important languages, as well as values, cultures, ideas, and ways of life.

The SNC does not take into account other Pakistani languages or the culture of Pakistan. To begin, ensure that students in Urdu classes 1–5 are exposed to Pakistani culture and local languages. There is a widespread disregard towards non-regional languages. Under the SNC, teaching "diversity of culture and languages" in Urdu is required. This means that the language will be utilised to facilitate the integration of all other languages and civilisations. Regional languages are respected because its speakers have political power, whereas the "others" are overlooked since they live on the outskirts of society. This is because regional languages are spoken by people who have political power. According to Jabeen (2020), the fixation of SNC with education's moral and political purposes as well as its insistence on Pakistan's cultural and linguistic variety make it an instrument of indoctrination and propaganda.

Research Objectives

1. To assess the implementation of Single National Curriculum in Public at primary level in District Rawalpindi.
2. To assess the opinion of teachers regarding usefulness of Single National Curriculum in Private schools at primary level in District Rawalpindi.
3. To compare the planning for implementation of Single National Curriculum in Public and Private Schools at primary level in District Rawalpindi.

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in implementation of Single National Curriculum in Public and Private schools at Primary level in Tehsil Kahuta.
2. There is no significant difference in opinion of teachers regarding usefulness of Single National Curriculum between Public and Private school teachers.
3. There is no significant difference in planning for implementation of Single National Curriculum in Public and Private schools.

Delimitations

Due to limited resources and time the current study was delimited to Tehsil Kahuta District Rawalpindi only.

Research Methodology

In this study the descriptive approach is used since it depends on values estimated with numbers and examined with statistical methods. The present research is descriptive in nature and survey type. This type of research includes gathering information that portrays occasions and after that tabulates, classifies, delineates, and describes the collected data. Primary level teachers of public

and private schools are the participants of this research from whom data is collected. All public and private schools in Tehsil Kahuta are included as a research population for this study. From both public and private schools fifty teachers have been included for data collection through random sampling, because random sampling gives an equal opportunity for each member of the defined sampling size. According to (Louis Cohen, Manionand, & Keith, 2007). The detail of sample is as under:

Table 1
Sample of Study

Sr. No.	Institutes	No of Schools
1	Govt. Schools	199
2	Private Schools	130
Total		329

Research Instrument

Self-constructed questionnaire has been used as a research instrument. The questionnaire distributed to schools through WhatsApp to gather data. All the questions of the questionnaire are aligned with research objectives of this study in order to evaluate the planning and implementation of SNC in public and private schools of Tehsil Kahuta. As this is a quantitative study. SPSS software is used for data analysis. Inferential and descriptive statistics is used to analyze data. In descriptive statistics, mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage was calculated. T-test is applied as inferential statistics to find significant difference between means of Public and private schools.

Results

Table 2
SNC Implementation Comparison

Sector	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Public	25	19.84	3.997	.044	.038
Private	25	21.72	1.838		

The table 2 explains that considerable differences of SNC implementation, public school shows (M=19.84, SD=3.89) and private schools show (M=21.72, SD=1.838) $t = .044$ and $p = .038$ shows that there is significant between two sectors. So we reject our first hypothesis as it is crystal clear that private schools has implemented SNC better them public schools.

Table 3
Implementation of SNC in public and private schools

Opinion	Public		Private	
	Frequency	Percent	Opinion	Frequency

Strongly agree	40	32.0	Strongly agree	52	41.6
Agree	58	46.4	Agree	64	51.2
Partially Agree	17	13.6	Partially Agree	9	7.2
Disagree	3	2.4	Disagree	0	0
Strongly Disagree	7	5.6	Strongly Disagree	0	0
Total	125	100.0	Total	125	100

Table 3 depicts that Public school teacher’s perception i.e.32.0 percent of the respondents were strongly agreed,46.4 percent of them were agreed that our school has implemented SNC, 13.6 percent partially agree 2.4 percent were disagree and 5.6 strongly disagreed about improper implementation. Private school teacher’ perceptions i.e.41.6 percent of the respondents were strongly agreed, 51.2 percent of them were agreed that our school implemented SNC, 7.2 percent partially agreed No teacher disagreed. 92% public schools and 100 % private schools implemented SNC; it reveals that SNC is implemented in almost all schools as per SOPs.

Table 4

Teachers’ opinion analysis regarding usefulness of SNC

Sector	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Public	25	19.72	3.247	0.306	0.59
Private	25	21.24	2.204		

The table 4 explains that considerable differences in the opinion of teachers regarding the usefulness of SNC, public school shows (M=19.72, SD=3.247) and private schools show (M=21.24, SD=2.204) and t = 0.306 having 0.59 P value shows that the results are significant. As per results private school teachers think that SNC is more useful as compared to public schools.

Table 5

Teachers’ opinion regarding the usefulness of SNC

Opinion	Public		Private		
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
Strongly agree	29	23.2	Strongly agree	47	37.6
Agree	68	54.4	Agree	62	49.6
Partially Agree	22	17.6	Partially Agree	16	12.8
Disagree	4	3.2	Disagree	0	0
Strongly Disagree	2	1.6	Strongly Disagree	0	0
Total	125	100	Total	125	100

Table 5 depicts that Public school teacher’s perception i.e.23.2 percent of the respondents were strongly agreed,54.4 percent of them were agreed that our school has implemented SNC, 17.6 percent partially agree 3.2 percent were disagree and 1.6 strongly disagreed about the success of SNC. Private school teacher’ perceptions i.e.37.6 percent of the respondents were strongly agreed, 49.6 percent of them were agreed that our school implemented SNC, 12.8 percent partially agreed.

No teacher disagreed. 95.2% public schools and 100 % private schools believe that SNC is useful for achieving its desired goals.

Table 6

t-test Analysis of Planning

Sector	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P
Public	25	36.88	6.559	0.407	0.113
Private	25	39.80	6.212		

The table 6 explains that the planning process in public and private school for SNC Implementation which shows considerable differences in the opinion of teachers regarding the implementation planning of SNC, public school shows (M=36.88, SD=6.559) and private schools show (M=3.980, SD=6.212) t= .407 and p value is 0.113 shows that the results are insignificant. There is difference between both sectors but it is not significant. As per result private schools planned implementation of SNC better public schools.

Table 7

Analysis of planning regarding implementation of SNC

Opinion	Public		Private		
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
Strongly agree	55	22.0	Strongly agree	66	26.4
Agree	109	43.6	Agree	133	53.2
Partially Agree	41	16.4	Partially Agree	32	12.8
Disagree	43	17.2	Disagree	18	7.2
Strongly Disagree	02	0.8	Strongly Disagree	01	0.4
Total	250	100	Total	250	100

Table 7 depicts that Public school teacher’s perception i.e.22.0 percent of the respondents were strongly agreed,43.6 percent of them were agreed that our school has implemented SNC, 16.4 percent partially agree 17.2 percent were disagree and 0.8 strongly disagreed about the proper planning of SNC. Private school teacher’ perceptions i.e.26.4 percent of the respondents were strongly agreed, 53.2 percent of them were agreed that our school implemented SNC, 12.8 percent partially agreed. 7.2 % disagreed and 0.4 % strongly disagreed that the planning of SNC was not proper. 82% public schools and 92.4 % private schools believe that SNC implementation planning was proper.

Conclusions

It was found that private schools had implemented SNC as per departmental instructions and as per SOPs as compared to public schools. The opinion regarding the usefulness of SNC is although there is not much difference between public and private schools but private schools think it is useful. As for as the planning for implementation is concerned there was significant difference in

public and private schools but as implementation and usefulness of SNC is concerned the result showed that both sector were not satisfied

Recommendations

Regardless of the socioeconomic status of their family, all kids should have equal access to education, which is why the implementation of a unified national curriculum is so important. It was also promised that all public and private schools, including Madaris, will participate in the implementation.

because they are a major source of knowledge for a large number of students. Making sure that the implementation takes place in both public and private schools is the responsibility of the administration. Since it is essential that these kids be enrolled in school in order to end the persistent educational gaps in Pakistan, the government should give the unenrolled children high priority. There are about 22.5 million school-age children in Pakistan who are not currently enrolled in school for a variety of reasons; all of these children cannot be served by the public school system as it stands. One option to build more schools and upgrade the facilities of those that are currently open is to increase the capacities of the public sector in order to meet the requirements. More financial resources will need to be allocated to educational institutions in order to realise this aim.

SNC must be implemented at the elementary and secondary levels along with improvements, since its effectiveness has been shown at the primary level. When SNC is expanded to encompass later phases in compliance with the true text and spirit of the curriculum, the intended objectives and goals of the National curriculum won't be achievable. By reducing the amount of unaffordable policies that hinder students' capacity for critical, analytical, and creative thought rather than promoting exceptional education, we can ensure that every child receives an education that is equal and consistent. There's a chance that repression will find its way into our educational system, so we must be very careful.

The design and execution of the following stages ought to be enhanced in light of the worries raised by the management of both public and private schools. Appropriate talks with all pertinent stakeholders must be made before proceeding to the following phases. While it is possible that we will see some strategic success, this would really be a sign of a poor-quality educational strategy gone wrong. The implementation of educational reforms and the planning of awareness seminars for all pertinent parties should be given top priority in order to promote and ease the movement of teachers and pupils amongst provinces. For educators to deliver the standardised curriculum in the most efficient way possible, they must be trained in compliance with the recently amended SNC. Teaching children new SNC should support their personal growth in all aspects.

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